

ECONOMY

CASH AND CASH EQUIVALENTS: ESSENCE AND IMPROVEMENT OF ACCOUNTING

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Abstract

The purpose of the article is to reveal the essence of cash and their equivalents and to determine directions for improving accounting. The theoretical and methodological basis of the research is a systematic approach to the study of the practical tools of accounting of cash and their equivalents. In the process of research and systematization of the obtained results, general scientific and special methods were used: abstract theoretical; historical; dialectical; induction and deduction, analysis and synthesis; formalization and comparison. The essence of the concepts "cash", "electronic money" and the components of cash equivalents are revealed. A proper definition of monetary funds is proposed - these are defined segments for non-cash and cash settlements between business entities; incomes and receipts, on the one hand, and expenses, on the other, which ensure optimal and efficient functioning of the monetary and credit system. Banks that have the right to issue electronic money with the name of electronic money/name of the payment system, using which operations with electronic money are carried out, have been determined. The proposals of various domestic scientists regarding the improvement of cash accounting were considered. It is proposed to make changes to the income and expenditure cash orders, supplementing them with separate data on operational, investment and financial activities, as well as a separate column in Journal-order No. 1 to display the amounts of transactions by types of economic activity (operational, financial and investment). Similarly, the order journals and information on account 31 "Bank accounts" and account 33 "Other funds" will be supplemented. This will facilitate the work of the accountant, optimize the document flow, improve analytical accounting at the enterprise in order to obtain detailed information on cash transactions by type of activity during the year and identify errors in accounting and tax accounting of cash transactions, and, as a result, strengthen responsibility among employees and prevent fines from tax authorities.

Keywords: accounting, cash, cash equivalents, electronic money, improvements.

Raising of problem. The availability of a certain amount of funds is an indispensable condition for starting and operating any business. In the course of carrying out production activities, capital constantly circulates: monetary form - production - commodity - monetary, and therefore, operations on spending and receipt of monetary funds are constantly taking place. Money belongs to those special categories that have always been the most relevant in economic thought since the interests of market subjects are manifested and implemented to the greatest extent in the process of money movement.

The importance of information on the flow of monetary funds and its equivalents is determined by the need to provide users with complete and unbiased information on financial status, performance, and monetary funds flow for decision-making. Operations related to the investment and financial activities of the enterprise are also reduced to repeated cash payments and receipts. The solvency, financial stability, and scalability of the enterprise's economic development largely depend on the extent to which different types of cash flows are coordinated with each other in terms of volume and time.

The importance and role of monetary funds and their equivalents for the activity of the enterprise determines the need for their separate research, determination of strategies and tactics for managing the formation and use of monetary funds flows, information about

which significantly affects the effectiveness of the management process of economic entities.

Analysis of researches and publications. The works of well-known domestic and foreign economists are devoted to the study of the accounting of monetary funds and their equivalents in market conditions, in particular, S.L. Bereza, M.T. Belukha, Yu.A. Veryga, S.F. Holova, N.G. Horytska, O.M. Gubachova, H.G. Kireitseva, M.V. Kuzhelny, N.M. Malyuga, L.V. Napadovskaya, V.O. Ozeran, M.S. Pushkar, V.V. Sopko, V.V. Tomchuk, B. Kolass, M.R. Matvii, V.V. Paliy, M.H.B. Perer, E.S. Hendriksen, G. Shillinglow and others. At the same time, there is a lack of comprehensive studies of accounting methods aimed at their improvement in domestic work.

Formulation of aims of the article. The purpose of the article is to specify the essence of monetary funds and their equivalents, since their identification in the accounting system and improvement of their display in accounting depends on the clear content of the categorical apparatus.

Exposition of basic material of research. Money is a multifunctional economic form that provides an accounting of value, exchange, payments, and accumulation of value and is one of the most important sections of the economy that contributes to its development. A well-functioning monetary system promotes full capacity utilization and full employment. If the monetary system does not function properly, it can cause sharp

fluctuations in the level of production, employment, and prices in the economy.

Currently, there are two main theories that compare the essence of the concepts of "money" and "monetary funds": formalistic (legal) and economic.

"Formalistic (legal)" interpretation of money is based on a literal interpretation of existing legal norms. According to this position, the legal concept of money is determined by the norms of the current law and is exhausted by them.

Figure 1 – "Formalistic (legal)" interpretation of the concept of "money"

* Source: [1]

The logic of the essence of the economic interpretation of money is depicted graphically in Figure 2.

Figure 2 – "Economic" interpretation of the concept of "money"

* Source: [2]

In order to avoid misunderstandings in the practical activities of enterprises, we consider it necessary to consider in detail the essence of the concept of "monetary funds" in regulatory documents (Table 1).

Table 1

Definition of the concept of "cash funds" in regulatory documents

Source	Definition
National Accounting Regulation (Standard) 1	Monetary funds - cash, funds in bank accounts, and demand deposits
Methodological recommendations for the analysis and assessment of the financial state of enterprises	Monetary funds - cash, funds in bank accounts, and demand deposits
Instruction "On Procedure of Preparing and Publishing Financial Reporting of Banks of Ukraine"	Monetary funds - cash in hand and interbank deposits on demand

* Source: [3]

So, all definitions of the concept of "monetary funds" given in regulatory documents are formulated so that they only list the components of this concept. According to regulatory documents, cash, funds in bank accounts and demand deposits should be classified as monetary funds. This wording is rather imperfect and needs to be clarified.

Let's consider the interpretation of the concept of "monetary funds" by other scientists (Table 2).

The "economic" interpretation of money is based on the premise that, along with cash money, there is also money in non-cash form. The considered approach to the concept of money was formed under the influence of the practice of trade turnover.

The logic of the essence of the formalistic (legal) interpretation of money is depicted graphically in Figure 1.

Table 2

Definition of the concept of "monetary funds"		
№	Author	Definition of the concept
1	Ostafiichuk, S.M.	Monetary funds is cash in the company's cash register, demand deposits, funds in bank accounts, which are characterized by absolute liquidity, that is, they can be used at any time for making payments, or exchanged for legal means of payment.
2	Osovskaya, H.V.	Monetary funds mean income and receipts that are accumulated in monetary form on the bank accounts of the enterprise, organization, or institution and are used to provide for their own needs or placement in the form of bank resources
3	Vysochan, O.S.	Monetary funds means funds in the cash register, electronic money, funds in current and other accounts in banks, which can be used at any time for making calculations in the process of carrying out economic transactions
4	Yefimenko, V.I., & Luk'ianenko, L.I.	Monetary funds are cash stored at the enterprise, money in banks (accounts); bank drafts, cashier's checks, and customer orders
5	Ishchenko, Ya.P., Podolianchuk, O.A., & Koval, N.I.	Monetary funds are a form of existence of money, used as a means of circulation and payment; banknotes and coins of the national currency of Ukraine, including commemorative and anniversary coins, which are in circulation and are valid means of payment
6	Kraevsky V.M.	Monetary funds means cash on hand, money in bank accounts, other monetary funds
7	Derii M.V.	Monetary funds are the main segments for making cash and non-cash payments between state budget institutions and enterprises
8	Neskhodovsky I.S.	Monetary funds is an abstract measure of economic processes, phenomena, and objects, which subjects agree to accept as a means of payment

* Source: [4-11]

The concept of monetary funds is usually used in accounting as income and receipts, but it is advisable to consider such a concept as "monetary funds" not as income and receipts, but also as expenses and financial results since the same monetary funds for debtors are used in calculations (sellers) are treated as income, and for creditors (buyers) - as expenses. As a result, these monetary funds provide a certain financial result.

Regarding the economic essence of monetary funds, we proposed our definition of monetary funds - these are defined segments for non-cash and cash settlements between business entities; incomes and receipts, on the one hand, and expenses, on the other, which ensure the optimal and efficient functioning of the monetary and credit system.

Along with absolutely liquid monetary funds, there are highly liquid assets - monetary funds equivalents.

Monetary funds equivalents are a separate economic category independent of monetary funds - a part of financial investments that is used not for calculations, but for maintaining the solvency of the enterprise, and repayment of its short-term obligations, which, if necessary, can be freely converted into known amounts of monetary funds with little risk of change in value.

Monetary funds equivalents are inherently a cross between monetary funds and current financial investments. They:

- as well as monetary funds are characterized by almost absolute liquidity;

- in contrast to monetary funds, which are valued at nominal value or the value indicated on the bank statement, monetary funds equivalents, as well as financial investments, are valued by the requirements of NP(S)BO 12 "Financial Investments" depending on the time of the valuation (upon acquisition, upon disposal, as of the balance sheet date) and the type of security (those held by the company until their maturity; other securities) [12];

- unlike monetary funds, they are capable of generating income;

- unlike current financial investments, they are held not to generate income, but to ensure the solvency of the business entity;

- as a rule, they are made for a shorter period than current financial investments (according to M(S)BO 7 monetary funds equivalents have a maturity of up to 3 months from the date of purchase [13]).

Based on this, in our opinion, the components of monetary funds equivalents are shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3 – Components of monetary funds equivalents

* Source: [4, 14]

So, monetary funds equivalents are related to cash because, like the latter, they are held to pay off short-term obligations, and not for investment or any other needs, but are capable of yielding some investment income as financial investments.

With the development of the Internet and information technologies in the field of electronic payments, a new economic category "electronic money" has emerged. The dynamics of the development of electronic money are accelerating all over the world, in particular in Ukraine. The frequency of use of electronic money in transactions for payment of goods and services by individuals, legal entities, and business entities is increasing. As a result of such processes, new types

of electronic money and new possibilities for transactions with them appear.

In modern economic literature, there is no unambiguous approach to the interpretation of the "electronic money" category. The main approach to understanding the essence of electronic money and its functional purpose is the position of electronic money in this way:

- means of payment used to pay for various goods and services;
- a substitute for monetary funds, which has an electronic form and is stored on electronic media and devices.

The main theoretical approaches to the definition of the term "electronic money" are systematized in Table 3.

Table 3

Approaches to defining the concept of "electronic money"		
№	The authors	Definition
1	Baranovskyi, O.I.	Electronic money is non-cash payments between sellers and buyers, banks and their clients, which are carried out using a computer network and communication systems using information coding and automatic processing.
2	Shyshkova, N.L.	Electronic money is a monetary obligation of the issuer, which must be exchanged for ordinary money at the request of the bearer; is an electronic record of a certain amount of value, which is protected by appropriate cryptographic algorithms.
3	Mokiienko, T.V., Pryidak, T.B., & Lipskyi, R.V.	Electronic money is a de facto substitute for the cash form of money, which is used for payments without the use of bank accounts, as well as exchange for cash, stored on special media and used with the help of special technical devices.
4	Demchenko, O.P., & Tsipstsiura, O.Yu.	Electronic money - units of value stored on an electronic device, accepted as a means of payment by persons other than the person who issues them and is also a monetary obligation of this person, performed in cash or non-cash form.
5	Law of Ukraine "About payment services"	Electronic money is units of value stored in electronic form, issued by the issuer of electronic money for payment transactions (including using prepaid multi-purpose payment cards), which are accepted as a means of payment by persons other than their issuer, and are monetary obligations of such issuer of electronic money.

* Source: [15-19]

So, electronic money does not have one specific definition, however, based on the given information, we can divide it into two groups such as card and network electronic money. The essence of card electronic money is that it is stored on special plastic cards that are issued by banks and used to purchase various goods, as well as pay for works and services. Network electronic money is in the form of money files stored on special media and devices. They can be used when paying for goods and services in online stores [16, p. 41].

The regulatory and legal framework that regulates the circulation of electronic money in Ukraine is the Resolution of the Board of the National Bank of Ukraine "About the approval of the Regulations on procedure for the issue of electronic means of payment and implementation of transactions with their use", the Law of Ukraine "About payment services".

Also, the current legislation has set limits on electronic money:

- for a non-replenishable electronic wallet, the maximum amount of electronic money should not exceed 5,000 UAH;
- for an electronic wallet that is replenished, the maximum amount of electronic money is set no higher than provided for in Art. 20 of the Law of Ukraine "On prevention and countermeasures against legalization (laundering) of proceeds obtained through crime, financing of terrorism and financing of the proliferation of weapons of mass destruction", i.e. 400,000 UAH [20].

As of January 17, 2023, according to the National Bank of Ukraine, only 6 banks have the right to issue electronic money.

Table 4

Banks that have the right to issue electronic money

№	Banks	<i>The name of the electronic money / the name of the payment system using which transactions with electronic money are carried out</i>
1	JSC "Sense Bank"	«ALFA-MONEY», MasterCard, Visa
2	PJSC "BANK VOSTOK"	PROSTIR
3	PJSC "TASCOMBANK"	«Maksi»
4	AB "UKRGASBANK"	PROSTIR
5	JSC "Raiffeisen Bank Aval"	MasterCard, Visa
6	PJSC "MTB BANK"	MasterCard, Visa, XPAY

* Source: [20]

Table 4 lists the banks and electronic money (payment systems) they issue and use for electronic money transactions.

In order to improve the regulatory and legal regulation of activities related to the issuance of electronic money and the implementation of payment transactions with it, the Resolution of the Board of the National Bank of Ukraine approved "Amendments to the Regulation on Payment Services and the Issuance of Electronic Money" dated June 29, 2023, No. 82 [21].

Thus, electronic money in a broad sense covers all types of digital representations of value, including virtual currencies and cashless money in banks.

In the current market conditions, most enterprises do not have enough cash assets, so it is quite important to have the ability to rationally distribute and use them. To do this, it is necessary to properly organize the accounting of monetary funds, to constantly improve it, as well as to be able to identify and solve problems that may arise during the accounting of transactions with monetary funds in the cash register and on bank accounts.

O. V. Popovych & T. Ya. Matkivska draws their attention to the problem of the completeness and timeliness of the display of monetary funds in the accounting system, because if the monetary funds are not fully and untimely recorded, then there will be no clear display of the real amount of funds. The consequence of this will be the incorrect display of tax charges. And such a mistake will entail some others, which can be punished with fines.

In order to eliminate both the above-mentioned problematic issues and other problems arising in the or-

ganization of accounting for cash transactions, the authors proposed the following ways of improving the accounting system in the field of monetary funds management [22]:

- further adaptation of the National accounting provisions regulating the organization and accounting of monetary funds to international standards;
- development and introduction of forms, methods, and mechanisms of the functioning of the management system of monetary funds accounting (for example, the introduction of an automated monetary funds flow management system at the enterprise, development of forms of management reporting on the movement of monetary funds and mechanisms for its compilation, etc.);
- expansion and improvement of forms and methods of settlement (clearing settlements, use of overdraft accounts, etc.);
- improvement and development of enterprise banking systems and technologies (corporate cards, "Client-Bank" system, etc.);
- development of mechanisms and methods for strengthening payment discipline and monitoring compliance with cash discipline (for example, carrying out an inventory of the cash register at least once a month, creating a petty cash fund, and entering the corresponding active account in the Chart of accounts);
- expansion and improvement of the legal framework for accounting of monetary funds at enterprises;
- the application of a monetary funds control system in enterprises, will make it possible to significantly increase the efficiency of the entire process of managing its activities;

– carrying out the development of financial plans for the receipt and expenditure of monetary funds for the next year, in which there will be a calculation of the planned income from the main activity and the expenditure of monetary funds in terms of expense items;

– creating a report on the receipt and use of monetary funds for the previous month and comparing it with normative (planned) indicators, which will ensure operational control over the movement of monetary funds at enterprises;

– implementation of full automation of monetary funds accounting, which will ensure high accuracy of accounting data related to the movement of monetary funds [22].

To generate accounting data on the receipt and expenditure of monetary funds in the context of ensuring the solvency of V.I. Kuz and T.O. Kitsen offer to form separate synthetic accounts, analytical accounts, and sub-accounts according to sources of income, and directions of spending monetary funds (in terms of types of activities, maintenance of production programs, strategic directions of development) [23].

The authors think that it would be appropriate to open management account 32 "Monetary funds flows by types (directions) of activity", to which such sub-accounts as 321 "Monetary funds flow from operating activities" and 322 "Monetary funds flow from financial activities" and 323 will be opened "Monetary funds flow from other activities".

According to V.I. Kuz and T.O. Kitsen, the proposed account in the accounting system will perform

transit functions, that is, it will serve only to accumulate data for management purposes. That is, the debit will show all the receipts of the business entity in terms of the identified areas of activity, and the credit will show spending. Thus, with the help of the proposed accounting tools, it is possible to track monetary funds balances, directions of loss, and determine the periodicity of monetary funds receipts [23].

In practice, this will not impose an additional burden on the accounting employee, since the data on the use of the transit account will be generated by the accounting software (additional setting) independently.

Today, a significant number of researchers note the need to improve existing accounts designed for accounting for electronic money. A.P. Sirotynska and O.P. Lesyk [24] suggest keeping track of the movement of electronic money in the WMU system "WebMoney" on account 315 "Electronic money", and A.S. Stovpova [25] suggests using account 32 "Electronic money" for synthetic accounting of electronic money, and performing analytical accounting in terms of types of electronic money.

Radchenko M.A. offers analytical accounting of transactions with electronic money to be conducted in the following directions at the enterprise:

– according to the selected electronic money system;

– by the notional currency of the wallet [26].

Yu.V. Yemelianova, and R.M. Tsyhan consider ways of improving monetary funds accounting at the enterprise and their main advantages (Table 5).

Table 5

Advantages of directions for improving monetary funds accounting

№	Directions for improving monetary funds accounting	Advantages
1	2	3
1	Using the system "Client-Bank"	1. efficiency in monetary funds management; 2. creation and editing of certain documents in offline mode; 3. the possibility of using one system to manage the accounts of several organizations;
		4. зручність використання програми. 5. можливість проводити платежі зі свого поточного рахунку в банку, не відвідуючи його, а з офісу підприємства; 6. економія часу
2	Payment of wages, bonuses and other payments to company employees to bank cards	1. the ability to settle with employees for wages, award bonuses, and issue advances for business trips in non-cash form; 2. a more convenient way of making payments for employees compared to cash payments; 3. will facilitate the accountant's work; 4. it will not be necessary to keep cash in the cash register and deposit it due to non-issuance within five days.
3	Development of a monetary funds accounting control program	1. the best way to check monetary funds flow; 2. possibility to check sources of income and usage in a short time;
4	Implementation of the petty cash fund	1. no accounts; 2. use of funds exclusively for minor expenses, which must be supported by a relevant document.
5	Distribution of duties	1. avoiding misrepresentations of accounts; 2. each MRP is solely responsible for its object; 3. excludes the possibility of abuse of office

* Source: [27]

Receipt and withdrawal of cash are processed by revenue (f. No. KO-1) and expenditure (f. No. KO-2) cash orders. Therefore, it is advisable to make changes to the income and expenditure cash orders, supplementing them with separate data on operational, investment, and financial activities [28].

The need for this information is very necessary because the cashier may or may not know to which type of activity to attribute this or that operation. In the corresponding column of the primary documents, the chief accountant or other responsible official should indicate the name of the type of activity: operational (opr.), investment (inv.), financial (fin.) or their code.

On the basis of the signed primary documents, the cashier fills in the cash book, indicating the amounts of transactions by type of activity. At the end of each working day, the cashier sums up the transactions for the day, determines the balance of money in the cash register for the next day, and transfers it to the accounting department, as a cashier's report, a tear-off sheet of the cash book with copies of the day's records and attached income and expenditure cash documents under the receipt in the cash book.

Amounts of cash received and transferred to bank institutions should also be reconciled with relevant bank statements for current accounts. After checking the cash report, the corresponding invoices are placed in a special column and Journal-order No. 1 and Sheet No. 1.1 are filled out.

To reduce the information load on the company's accounting at the end of the year, we additionally offer to display the sums of transactions by types of economic activity (operational, financial, and investment) in Order Journal No. 1 in a separate column. Similarly, order journals and information on account 31 "Bank accounts" and account 33 "Other funds" will be supplemented [28].

The cash flow indicators grouped in this way will serve as an information base for filling in analytical data for accounts 30, 31, 33 of journal-order No. 1, 2, and information. The practical application of the proposals on the construction of primary documents and relevant registers will reduce the filling of the Cash Flow Statement to a simple transfer of information from the accounting registers to the Statement, which will not cause difficulties, additional costs of working time for the accountant.

Conclusions. The evolution of money indicates a constant approach to matching its form and content. In the financial statements of economic entities, the category "money" is replaced by the category "cash". There is no doubt that the main characteristic that should be taken into account when classifying assets as cash is liquidity, that is, the ability of an asset to quickly turn into a legal means of payment with minimal loss of its value. Monetary funds include cash in the company's cash register, demand deposits, and funds in bank accounts, which are characterized by absolute liquidity, i.e. can be used at any time for making calculations or exchanged for legal means of payment and should be classified as cash.

The use by enterprises in a complex of all the proposed measures regarding the improvement of the organization of monetary funds and their equivalents will provide an opportunity to improve the enterprise's calculations and accounting. The proposed measures will facilitate the accountant's work, optimize document flow, improve analytical accounting at the enterprise in order to obtain detailed information on cash transactions by type of activity during the year and identify errors in accounting and tax accounting of cash transactions, and, as a result, strengthen responsibility among employees and prevent fines from tax authorities. The outlined problems of the essence and improvement of the accounting of cash and their equivalents are becoming more and more relevant over time, so such research should be continued to help everyone find high-quality, verified, useful information that will become a weapon of business in the conditions of martial law.

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